
Exploring the Patterns of Time Management among Women Homemakers in Sagolband Constituency

Kangjam Umabati Devi

Research Scholar, Department of Home Science, Bir Tikendrajit University, Canchipur

Kangabam Sulochana Devi

Associate Professor, Department of Home Science, Bir Tikendrajit University

Y. Prabhabati Devi

Sr. Scientist and Head, KVK, Imphal East, CAU, Imphal

Email ID: kangjamumabati@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Time management plays a crucial role in the efficient functioning of households, especially among homemakers who are primarily responsible for organizing and performing daily domestic activities. This study titled “Exploring the Pattern of Time Management among the—Women Homemakers in Sagolband Constituency” seeks to examine how homemakers allocate and utilize their time across various household tasks. The research focuses on identifying the daily time schedules, task prioritization methods, adherence to time plans, and the challenges faced in managing time effectively. A descriptive research design was employed, and data were collected from a sample of women homemakers residing in Sagolband constituency through structured interviews and questionnaires. The findings reveal distinct patterns in the division of time between routine domestic chores, childcare, leisure, and social activities. While many respondents follow an informal time plan, factors such as family size, occupation, and socio-economic status significantly influence their time management practices. The study highlights the need for better awareness and

planning strategies to enhance time utilization, reduce workload stress, and improve overall household efficiency.

Introduction

Time management is widely recognized as a fundamental component of effective household functioning. It involves planning, organizing, and allocating time to various activities to maximize efficiency and reduce stress (Claessens et al., 2007). For women homemakers, effective time management is particularly crucial, as they perform a diverse range of unpaid domestic tasks including cooking, cleaning, childcare, caregiving, and household maintenance. Despite its central role in sustaining families and communities, this labour remains undervalued in economic terms and often goes unmeasured in formal statistics (Bianchi et al., 2000).

In many societies, including India, gender norms and cultural expectations assign the bulk of domestic responsibilities to women, irrespective of their participation in paid employment. Studies have consistently shown that women spend a significantly greater proportion of their time on unpaid domestic and care work compared to men (Chopra & Zambelli, 2017). This unequal distribution of time responsibilities often limits women's opportunities for education, employment, leisure, and personal growth. Consequently, efficient time management practices are essential not only for maintaining household functionality but also for supporting women's overall well-being and empowerment.

The context of Sagolband constituency in Imphal West district, Manipur, offers a unique setting to examine patterns of time management among homemakers. Sagolband is characterized by a blend of traditional Meitei socio-cultural structures and modern urban lifestyles, resulting in a dynamic environment where homemakers must balance conventional domestic roles with evolving social and economic demands. However, there is a noticeable paucity of empirical research exploring how women homemakers in this specific constituency plan and allocate their time across daily household, family, and personal activities.

This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the patterns of time management among women homemakers in Sagolband constituency. It seeks to examine their daily time allocation, task prioritization strategies, influence of socio-economic and the factors on their time management practices. The findings are expected to contribute to a deeper understanding of how homemakers navigate their multiple roles and responsibilities, and to inform interventions and programs that can support more effective time use, enhance household productivity, and promote gender equity within the domestic sphere.

Objective of the study

The study was conducted with the following objective:

To explore the patterns of time management practiced by women homemakers in Sagolband constituency, with special focus on their allocation of time across household, family, and personal activities.

Research Design

The present study employed a **descriptive research design** to explore and analyze the patterns of time management among women homemakers in Sagolband constituency. A descriptive approach was chosen because it enables systematic collection and presentation of data to provide an accurate picture of existing time management practices without manipulating any variables.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in **Sagolband constituency**, located in Imphal West district of Manipur. This area was selected due to its distinctive socio-cultural context, which reflects a combination of traditional Meitei household structures and modern urban influences. The diversity in household types and socio-economic status within the constituency makes it a suitable setting for examining variations in time management patterns among homemakers.

The population and sample

Target population consisted of **women homemakers** residing in Sagolband constituency. A total of **100 respondents** were selected using **stratified random sampling** to ensure representation from different localities within the area. The sample was divided into two groups:

- **Working homemakers** (N = 50): Women engaged in part-time or full-time paid work in addition to household responsibilities.
- **Non-working homemakers** (N = 50): Women who are exclusively involved in household activities without any formal employment.

This categorization allowed for meaningful comparison of time management patterns between the two groups.

Tools for Data Collection

A **structured interview schedule and questionnaire** were developed as primary tools for data collection. The questionnaire comprised both closed- and open-ended questions covering the following aspects:

- Demographic and socio-economic profile
- Daily time allocation for various household, family, and personal activities
- Task prioritization strategies
- Time planning methods and adherence levels
- Challenges faced in managing time effectively

The tools were pre-tested with a small group of respondents to check for clarity, reliability, and cultural appropriateness. Necessary modifications were made based on feedback before final administration.

Procedure of Data Collection

Data were collected through **face-to-face interviews** and **self-administered questionnaires**, depending on the literacy level and convenience of the respondents. Interviews were conducted in the local language to ensure accurate understanding and response. Data collection was carried out over a period of four weeks.

Data Analysis

The collected data were coded, tabulated, and analysed using **descriptive statistical methods** such as frequency distributions, percentages, and cross-tabulations. Comparative analysis between working and non-working homemakers was performed to identify significant differences in time allocation and management strategies. The results were presented in tables and graphs for clarity and ease of interpretation.

Limitation of the study

Although the study provides valuable insights into the time management patterns of women homemakers in Sagolband constituency, it has certain limitations. First, the study is limited to a single constituency and a sample of 100 respondents, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to other regions. Second, the data are based on self-reported information, which may be influenced by recall bias or social desirability. Finally, the study focuses primarily on descriptive analysis. Despite these limitations, the

study offers a meaningful contribution to understanding time management practices among homemakers in a specific socio-cultural setting.

Review of literature

Time management has been a central topic in studies related to household functioning, gender roles, and productivity. It involves the effective planning, prioritization, and utilization of time to accomplish various tasks within limited time frames (Claessens et al., 2007). The literature reveals that women, particularly homemakers, play a pivotal role in managing household activities and resources. Their ability to plan and allocate time efficiently is closely linked to household well-being, personal development, and socio-economic progress.

Time Management and Household Work

Bianchi et al. (2000) conducted a comprehensive study on the gender division of household labour in the United States and found that women continue to spend significantly more time on domestic work compared to men, despite changes in workforce participation patterns. This imbalance highlights the critical need for time management strategies among homemakers. Similarly, Oakley (1974) emphasized that domestic labour, though essential, remains undervalued and invisible in economic statistics, which contributes to limited institutional support for homemakers' time-related needs.

In the Indian context, several studies have examined how cultural norms shape the distribution of time. Menon (2012) observed that Indian women spend approximately five to six hours daily on household chores, irrespective of their employment status. The study pointed out that time allocation is influenced by family structure, socio-economic background, and the presence of domestic help.

Socio-Economic and Cultural Influences

Socio-economic characteristics significantly influence how women allocate and manage their time. According to Budlender (2008), factors such as household size, income levels, and access to infrastructure affect the amount of time women spend on unpaid domestic work. In regions with limited access to time-saving technologies, homemakers tend to spend longer hours on routine chores, leaving less time for leisure or self-development.

In the North Eastern region of India, including Manipur, socio-cultural traditions often reinforce women's role as primary caregivers and household managers (Singh & Devi, 2013). Such cultural

expectations shape their daily routines and time-use patterns. However, modernization and urbanization are gradually altering these patterns, creating a mix of traditional and modern time management practices.

Task Prioritization and Time Planning

Effective time management is not only about how much time is spent but also how tasks are prioritized and planned. Macan et al. (1990) highlighted that individuals who engage in structured time planning experience greater control over their daily activities and lower stress levels. For homemakers, prioritization is often based on urgency and family needs rather than personal goals (Chopra & Zambelli, 2017). This indicates that their time management practices are shaped more by external expectations than by self-directed planning.

Gaps in Literature

While international and national studies provide valuable insights into time management practices, there is limited literature focusing specifically on **homemakers in Sagolband constituency, Manipur**. Existing studies rarely examine how cultural, social, and economic factors intersect to influence time management in this unique socio-cultural setting. This gap highlights the need for localized research to understand homemakers' time use patterns, planning strategies, and constraints.

Results and Discussion

The results of the study present a detailed analysis of the time management patterns practiced by women homemakers in Sagolband constituency. The findings are discussed in relation to daily time allocation, task prioritization, and adherence to time plans, with comparisons drawn between working and non-working homemakers. These results are interpreted in the light of existing literature to highlight emerging trends and contextual factors influencing time use.

Table 1: Personal Characteristics of Respondents

Personal Characteristics	Working (N-50)	Non-Working (N-50)	Total (N-100)
Age			
Below-20	5 (10%)	15 (30%)	20 (40%)

20-34	22 (44%)	24 (48%)	46 (92%)
35 and above	23 (46%)	11 (22%)	34 (68%)
Educational Level			
Illiterate	Nil	Nil	Nil
Primary	5 (10%)	5 (10%)	10 (20%)
Secondary	12 (24%)	18 (36%)	30 (60%)
Graduate	23 (46%)	21 (42%)	44 (88%)
Post Graduate	10 (20%)	6 (12%)	16 (32%)
Employment Status			
Working	50 (50%)		50 (50%)
Non-Working	-	50 (50%)	50 (50%)

The above table 1 shows the average age of the housewives was 30, and they were in the 20–35 age range (Table 1). The age group's maximum number of working respondents was 30 years of age or older. Compared to 88% of respondents who finished their education all the way to graduation, only 20% of respondents studied through the primary level. The entire sample was made up of 50% working people and 50% non-working people (Table 1). All respondents (100%) were members of a nuclear family. The household makes between Rs. 5000 and Rs. 50,000 and more.

Among **working women**, **56%** gave a “Yes” response, while **44%** responded “No.” In contrast, among **non-working women**, only **20%** responded “Yes,” whereas a significant majority, **80%**, responded “No.” This clearly indicates that **working women were more likely to respond positively** compared to non-working women. The difference between the two groups suggests that employment status influences their response pattern, with working women showing a **higher level of agreement or participation** than non-working women.

Fig. 1. Distribution of frequency of reasons for having specific time plan

The above fig.1. indicates that among **working women**, the most common reason was **flexibility (92.8%)**, followed by **stress reduction (85.7%)** and **efficiency/productivity (71.4%)**. This highlights their emphasis on managing professional and personal tasks efficiently. Among **non-working women**, the strongest reason was **improved family dynamics (100%)**, followed by **efficiency/productivity (80%)**. Their responses were more family-oriented rather than career-focused. **Work-life balance** was more important to working women (64.2%) compared to non-working women (40%). **Consistency and routine** were the least cited reason for both groups (35.7% vs. 20%), showing that it was not a primary motivator. Overall, working women tend to focus on **flexibility, stress management, and balancing multiple roles**, while non-working women prioritized **family harmony and productivity at home**.

Fig. 2. Distribution of frequency of reasons for not having specific time plan

The above fig.2. presents the distribution of reasons cited by working and non-working women for not adhering to a specific time plan.

Both working and non-working groups emphasized **flexibility** and **avoiding** as key reasons for not following strict time plans. However, **working women focus more on reducing pressure**, likely due to

the dual demands of home and workplace. In contrast, **non-working women give more importance to stress-free household management, less perfectionism, and creative flow**. These findings indicate that while both groups value adaptability, the underlying motivations differ depending on their employment status.

The higher percentage among working women can be attributed to the need for systematic time management in order to balance their dual roles in workplace and household responsibilities. Planning their daily schedule enables them to complete multiple tasks efficiently within limited time.

On the other hand, the **majority of non-working women (80.0%) do not follow any planned daily schedule**. This may be due to their relatively flexible routines and the absence of external time-bound work commitments. Non-working women may rely more on spontaneous decision-making in household activities rather than pre-planned schedules.

Both groups show a small percentage of women who rarely follow plans, but it is slightly higher among non-working women (10%) compared to working women (3.6%).

Non-working women appear more regular in following a planned routine. **Working women face greater variability**, likely due to balancing professional and domestic responsibilities.

The findings indicate that **task prioritization is an integral part of daily activity management** among both groups, though it appears slightly more prevalent among working women, reflecting their need for structured time allocation in balancing multiple roles.

Table 2: Distribution of frequency of how the work are set priorities

*How the works are set priorities	Working women N-38		Non-working N-35	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Urgency of the work	27	71.0	22	62.8
Importance	25	65.8	27	77.1
Needs of family	31	81.5	34	97.1
Habitual routine	17	44.7	20	57.1

*Multiple Response

The table 2. reveals that both groups gave the highest weight to **needs of the family**. Non-working women (97.1%) were more inclined than working women (81.5%). This shows that family responsibility dominates decision-making in both categories.

For both groups, **needs of family** remain the central criterion. **Working women** lean towards **urgency**, reflecting time pressure. **Non-working women** lean towards **importance** and **habitual routine**, reflecting more flexible time and structured daily habits.

Fig. 3. Distribution of frequency of time spent on cooking

The fig.3. reveals that a majority of working women (54%) spent less than 30 minutes on the activity, compared to only 18% of non-working women. Non-working women were more likely (60%) to spend 30 min – 1 hour on it, whereas only 36% of working women did so. For more than 1 hour, non-working women (22%) still outnumber working women (10%).

This suggests that working women, likely due to time constraints, spent significantly less time on the activity compared to non-working women.

Fig. 4. Distribution of frequency of time spent on cleaning utensils

The fig.4. shows a **clear time-use gap** between working and non-working women. Working women cluster heavily in the shortest time category, while non-working women dominate the middle and longer time categories. This difference reflects how **employment reduces available time for household or personal task.**

Fig. 5. Distribution of frequency of time spent on household cleaning

The above fig.5. clearly shows that **working women cluster in shorter time categories**, while **non-working women were more present in longer time categories**. This likely reflects **employment-related time constraints** versus **availability for extended engagement** among non-working women.

Fig. 6. Distribution of frequency of time spent on washing clothes

The data presented in fig.6. highlights the time distribution spent on washing clothes among working and non-working women. It is observed that a majority of **working women (48%)** spend between **30 minutes to 1 hour** on washing clothes, followed by **32%** who spend more than one hour, and only **20%** who complete the task in less than 30 minutes.

In contrast, among **non-working women**, the highest proportion (**56%**) spend more than **1 hour** on washing clothes, while **34%** spend between **30 minutes to 1 hour**, and only **10%** take less than 30 minutes.

This variation indicates that **non-working women devote more time to washing clothes** compared to working women. The difference can be attributed to the **time constraints faced by working women**, who may prefer **faster or more efficient methods**, such as the use of washing machines or multitasking during the process, in order to manage both household and professional responsibilities. On the other hand, non-working women may have **more flexible schedules**, allowing them to spend longer durations on such household chores, possibly doing it manually or with more attention to detail.

Majority of the non-working women were more involved in **traditional, time-consuming leisure** (gardening, arts & crafts) whereas **Working women** dominated in **digital leisure** (social media), reflecting lifestyle differences. Activities like **reading and watching movies** show **balanced participation**, cutting across employment status. Employment status **influences leisure choice** – working women prefer quick, tech-based activities, while non-working women engage in home-based, creative, and outdoor ones.

Implications of the Study

- The study provides useful insights into the time management patterns of women homemakers, helping to understand how household responsibilities are organized in Sagolband constituency.
- It highlights the need for awareness and training programs on effective time planning and task scheduling to improve household efficiency.
- The findings emphasize the importance of introducing simple time-saving methods and technologies to reduce workload and stress among homemakers.
- Socio-economic and cultural factors influencing time use should be considered in developing gender-sensitive policies and community support systems.
- The study serves as a baseline for future research on time use and women's roles in household management in similar socio-cultural contexts.

Suggestions

- **Time Management Training:** Organize community workshops and awareness programs to train homemakers in effective time planning, task prioritization, and scheduling techniques.
- **Use of Time-Saving Methods:** Encourage the adoption of simple, cost-effective time-saving tools and household technologies to reduce the time spent on routine chores.
- **Family Participation:** Promote greater involvement of family members in household activities to share responsibilities and reduce the workload on homemakers.
- **Policy Support:** Develop gender-sensitive policies that recognize unpaid domestic work and provide institutional support through local bodies or women's organizations.

- **Further Research:** Conduct more extensive studies with larger and more diverse samples to explore time management practices in different socio-economic and cultural contexts.
- **Personal Development Opportunities:** Create avenues for homemakers to engage in educational, skill-building, or leisure activities by improving time allocation and reducing household drudgery.

Conclusion

The study highlights the patterns of time management practiced by women homemakers in Sagolband constituency, revealing variations based on socio-economic and cultural factors. Effective time planning and task prioritization play a vital role in improving household efficiency and reducing workload stress. The findings emphasize the need for awareness, family support, and policy interventions to enhance homemakers' time use and overall well-being.

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